

Speculation on the Role of Information in the Microcanonical and Shannon's Entropy Cases

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The microcanonical approach to describing an isolated system of N particles with a total energy of E , weights each energy distribution scheme $\{n_i\}$ with the same constant weight so as to remove all possible extra information. In other words, if one particular distribution scenario is weighted more than another there would be extra information justifying this condition. As a result, when calculating the number of states for a microcanonical system (in order to create Entropy = $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$) one considers a sum of all possible energy distributions over N particles with total E , e.g. (1). On the other hand, the Shannon entropy case is related to picking only one distribution of E over N (one macrostate) as argued in (2). In (1), Stirling's approximation and the method of steepest descent is applied to the microcanonical approach and a Shannon type result with corrections emerges.

The point we make in this note is that in going from the microcanonical to the Shannon result, one essentially chooses one macrostate with minimum information. As a result, the others are ignored and we ask whether it is really the case that all states represent equal weight in the microcanonical scheme. Given that the Shannon approximation does not even consider these states it is not clear that the microcanonical scheme is particularly relevant.

For example, we consider N particles, with $N-1$ having 0 energy and one, E . This is a member of the equal weight set, but realistically seems to represent a non-equilibrium scenario. The single particle with E will collide with one particle, then two moving particles may collide etc, as the system moves toward equilibrium. This is not the viewpoint of a die (which is also linked with a uniform distribution) because with a die toss one may obtain any of the 6 possible results at any toss. $N-1$ particles with energy 0 and 1 with E does not allow one to obtain any of the equally weighted energy distributions. Thus, energy distributions with energy skewed towards a few particles do not seem to represent equilibrium scenarios. As a result, one may argue for simply ignoring the microcanonical distribution and seeking the one macrostate which minimizes information, i.e. $N p_i = \text{number of outcomes for a given a priori } p_i$, where i represents a state of a single particle. This is in fact the Shannon result.

In other words, we suggest choosing the Shannon $N p_i$ state a priori and then dealing with fluctuations. Even in the case of choosing fluctuations, it is not clear that all small deviations from the equilibrium $N p_i$ macrostate really carry equal weight because physical dynamics is involved in changing from one macrostate to another and one cannot use minimization of information to bypass some physical information that may actually exist. In other words, there may be dynamical constraints in an interacting system which break the equal weight of any distribution of E over N even for states very similar to the $N p_i$ one, we argue.

Microcanonical Distribution

A microcanonical distribution of an isolated system with N particles and total energy E seems to suggest that any distribution set $\{n_i\}$ of E over N carries the same weight. This is certainly a minimum information suggestion, but we argue that a problem with this scenario is that there

are physical interactions which transform one state into another and so it may not be the case that one has a uniform distribution.

If one considers a die, then for any toss one has an equal probability of obtaining any side. If one has a gas and $N-1$ particles have 0 energy and the 1 has E , this would seem to be a non-equilibrium situation, but the microcanonical approach indicates that it is one distribution of an equilibrium which carries the same weight as any other (which respects N, E). The problem is that given 1 particle with E , one can only transition to a very constrained set of $\{n_i\}$ i.e. at first only one collision may occur, then two etc. This is not an equilibrium picture, but a mixture of determinism and stochasticity as one moves in a somewhat deterministic way towards equilibrium. As a result, highly skewed energy states (with a few particles having all of the energy) would really be considered non-equilibrium states, we suggest.

Furthermore, we argue that one could a priori seek a single macrostate which minimizes information and not argue that this state has to follow from a microcanonical approach as an approximation. One may simply and directly find the macrostate with minimum entropy.

Shannon's Entropy and the Macrostate with Minimum Information

Instead of assigning equal weight to all distributions of E over N , one may seek the macrostate with the minimum information. We argue that for large N , this is:

$$N p_i = \text{number of single particles in state } i \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is the simplest way of guessing the number of outcomes of i given N and p_i and so represents the minimal information. This leads to Shannon's entropy because:

$$\text{Probability} = \text{Product over } i \text{ } p_i \text{ power } (p_i N) \rightarrow \ln(\text{Probability}) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } N p_i \ln(p_i). \quad ((2))$$

Alternatively, in keeping with the microcanonical approach, one may write:

$$1 = \left\{ \text{Sum over } i \text{ } p_i \right\} \text{ power } N = \text{Sum over } \{n_i\} \text{ Product over } \{n_i\} \frac{N!}{n_i!} \text{ Product over } \{n_i\} p_i \text{ power } n_i \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{Here } \{n_i\} \text{ is a set such that } \text{Sum over } i \text{ } n_i = N \text{ and } \text{Sum over } e_i \text{ } n_i = E \quad ((4))$$

((3)) represents the microcanonical equal weight picture. If one state dominates the sum (and the rest are essentially 0), then:

$$\ln(1) = \ln \left(\text{Product over } \{n_i\} \frac{N!}{n_i!} \text{ Product over } \{n_i\} p_i \text{ power } n_i \right) \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{This yields Stirling's approximation (first order) } \ln(n!) = n \ln(n) \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is identical to the $N p_i$ minimal information picture.

We argue that one does not really need to know about the microcanonical approach to seek a priori a single macrostate with minimal information. In fact, we argue that there may be no reason to consider macrostates with almost all of the energy assigned to a few particles as being part of the equilibrium picture.

Fluctuations About the Minimal Informational State

Given that the Shannon picture of a single macrostate represented by $N_{pi}=n_i$ is taken to represent the minimal information macrostate and that dynamics are important, it is not clear that the equal weight for macrostates applies at all in a gas. If that is the case, one could bypass the microcanonical picture and simply focus on fluctuations from $N_{pi} = n_i$. It is possible that of the various fluctuations δn_i such that:

$$\sum_i \delta n_i = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i \delta n_i = 0 \quad ((7))$$

are not of equal weight due to dynamics. For example, there may be a higher weight for changes which do not skew the $N_{pi} = n_i$ distribution as much. In other words, a fluctuation which increases n_1, n_2, n_3 by a large amount is skewed and may have less of a probability than one which involves many more smaller δn_i .

In (1), a microcanonical approach is used to calculate the number of states of a three-level scheme, using essentially ((3)). Stirling's approximation, to second order, $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) - n$ is used, and the steepest descent method applied. This method, however, evaluates $\int dx \exp(\phi(x))$ at x_{max} , i.e.

$$\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{-\frac{d^2\phi}{dx^2} \text{ at } x_{max}}} \exp(\phi(x_{max})) \quad ((8))$$

Ultimately, however, $\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{-\frac{d^2\phi}{dx^2} \text{ at } x_{max}}}$ is considered $\ll \exp(\phi(x_{max}))$ and so the entire microcanonical scheme becomes:

$$\exp(\phi(x_{max}))$$

with this term essentially applying to one peaked macrostate because $\exp(\phi(x))$ is the integrand. We argue that there is essentially no microcanonical approach used in the first place in any meaningful way.

As a result, it may not be the case that the microcanonical scheme which applies equal weights to all $\{n_i\}$ sets such that $\sum_i n_i = N$ and $\sum_i e_i n_i = E$ is actually the starting point of statistical analysis of a gas.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the microcanonical approach to an isolated system of N particles with total energy E assigns equal weight to all sets $\{n_i\}$ such that $\sum_i n_i = N$ and $\sum_i e_i n_i = E$. We argue that although this does remove much information, physical interactions are required to

transition from one macrostate to another and so this uniform distribution is not the same as a toss of die for which any result is possible at any toss. If 1 particle has E and $N-1$ have 0 energy, this seems to be a non-equilibrium situation which slowly moves to equilibrium as more and more collisions occur. Thus, strongly skewed states should not be part of the equilibrium picture, we argue. In fact, we suggest that one might forgo the microcanonical approach altogether and a priori seek a single macrostate which minimizes information, i.e. the usual $Np_i = n_i$. In such a case, even fluctuations about this state, i.e. $\{ \delta n_i \}$, such that $\sum_i \delta n_i = 0$ and $\sum_i e_i \delta n_i = 0$ do not necessarily carry the same weight. For example, there may be a smaller weight for fluctuations which are concentrated about a few i levels and ignore the rest.

References

1. Lia, Y. Entropy and Temperature of the Three Level System: The Microcanonical Ensemble Method 2021 DOI:10.5506/APhysPolB.52.467
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Stirling's Approximation and Information Theory Part 2 (zenodo, preprint, 2025)